

both seasons, except with 150 kg N/ha as PU and 120 kg N/ha as NECU in 1988 (see table). NECU at 90 and 120 kg N/ha gave yields similar to those of PU at 120 and 150 kg N/ha.

The superiority of NECU to PU is also shown by the quadratic response functions:

$$\text{for PU, } Y = 3543 + 18N - 0.011N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99;$$

$$\text{for NECU, } Y = 3556 + 31N - 0.056N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99,$$

where Y is yield in kg/ha.

The correlation ($r = 0.98^{**}$) between productive tillers and average grain yield was significant and positive. ■

Integrated pest management – diseases

Outbreak of leaf and neck blast in boro rice crop in Bangladesh

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Epidemics of blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* have been recurring in Bangladesh every 3 or 4 yr. In the 1990 dry season (boro) crop, leaf (LBI) and neck blast (NBI) on both local and modem cultivars were higher in some locations than they had been the previous 2 yr. NBI incidence during rice crop maturity (Mar-Apr 1990) was so severe, we surveyed outbreaks in different regions.

Disease incidence (%) was assessed in 25-35 fields/region by counting the number of infected and healthy tillers or panicles of 3 × 3 hills in 9 sampling spots taken in a diagonal direction per field. Severity was rated on a 0-9 scale. The cultivars grown and prevailing tempera-

ture, humidity, and rainfall also were recorded.

The outbreak covered an average 45% of the area planted to boro rice, although its intensity varied across locations. Incidence and severity were higher in the northeastern part of the country than in the northern and southwestern parts. Disease occurred on crops growing on all types of land and soil types (see table). In region I, plots with severe NBI were also affected by low temperature.

During Jan-Mar 1990, humidity was higher at 0600 h and 1200 h, and the difference between maximum and minimum temperature was less than in 1989 (see figure). The high humidity was unusual, and frequent but light rainfall during the period kept rice leaves wet for longer periods in the morning. This favored blast development.

The cultivars grown in the different regions had not changed during the last few years. The reason for the 1990 blast outbreak appears to be related to weather. ■

Incidence and severity of leaf and neck blast in 1990 dry season crops in some regions of Bangladesh.

Region ^a	Area planted (x10 ³ ha)	Fields examined (no.)	Area infected (%)	Land type	Soil type	Incidence (%)		Severity (0-9)	
						LB1	NB1	LB1	NB1
I	179	28	22.8	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	10-100	5-9	3-9
II	605	35	94.1	Low medium high	Sandy loam to clay loam	3-50	1-20	3-9	2-5
III	339	25	4.5	Low medium	Clay loam	1-85	1-75	2-9	5-9
IV	215	34	19.4	Low medium	Sandy loam	2-10	1-30	1-3	1-2
V	139	27	50.0	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	5-50	4-9	1-3
All	1477	149	44.7	Low-high	Sandy loam to clay	1-100	1-100	1-9	1-9

^a I = Greater Dhaka district, II = Greater Tangail and Mymensingh districts, III = Greater Sylhet district, IV = Greater Rangpur and Dinjpur districts, V = Greater Khulna and Jessore districts. Cultivars grown: I = BR1, BR2, BR11, BR14, IR8, Pajam, and locals; II = BR1, IR8, BR14, Pajam, Purbachi, and locals; III = BR3, BR14, BR17, BR18, IR8, Pajam, and locals; IV = BR9, BR14, and locals; V = IR50, Purbachi, Ratna, and locals.

Prevailing relative humidity (RH), temperature, and number of rainy days, Jan-Mar 1989 and 1990.

Effect of plant extracts in controlling rice tungro

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We screened 32 plant species belonging to 23 families for their ability to control tungro (see list).

Extracts were prepared by grinding plant tissues with sterile water, at 1 ml water/g of tissue, in a mortar and pestle. The macerate was expressed through cotton wool and diluted by adding sterile water to 10% concentration (wt/vol). Detergent was added at 1 ml/liter of extract and the mixture sprayed on 15-d-old ADT31 rice seedlings.

Seedlings were inoculated with viruliferous green leafhoppers *Nephotettix*